

Recommended citation

Wickramasinghe, V., & Malik, K. (2016). Exploring motivations for university-industry collaboration in Sri Lanka. [R&D Management Conference 2016 “From Science to Society: Innovation and Value Creation”](https://pure.manchester.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/51573435/2016_RnD_Management_Full_paper_VW_KM_FINAL.pdf), pp. 1-8, July 3-6, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK
https://pure.manchester.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/51573435/2016_RnD_Management_Full_paper_VW_KM_FINAL.pdf

Exploring motivations for university-industry collaboration in Sri Lanka

Abstract: Many advanced economies are at the forefront of the growth of university-industry collaborations. But many developing countries have yet to fully implement this type of important linkage phenomenon. We report some initial findings from our study conducted in Sri Lanka, which shows that fostering some individual level engagement skills would appear to be helpful, not only for increasing the volume of university-industry relations but also their impact. Our questionnaire survey to Sri Lankan universities has confirmed that most existing collaborations with industry are based around student placements in firms and some academics providing individual consultancy to industrial firms. Another important finding in the context of developing countries is that some industrial firms simply remain ignorant as to what universities can provide in terms of new knowledge and support for the firm. Similarly, some universities seem to be unaware of the range of different mechanisms available to explore collaborations and interactions with industrial firms. Some key practical implications are presented, where we argue that the remit of university-industry collaborative projects (e.g. R&D collaboration) might sometimes be too complex to implement in a developing country setting. Hence the risk of failure becomes high, ultimately resulting in some loss of trust between the collaborating partners.

1. Introduction

Although there is abundant evidence to suggest that different forms of knowledge transfer occurs between universities and industrial firms, for example via informal contacts, personnel mobility, consulting relationships and joint research projects, most of this evidence is reported from developed country experiences. Therefore we aim to provide some current insights into this important activity from a developing country perspective via exploratory empirical findings obtained from Sri Lanka. As some types of university-industry collaborations are still in their infancy in Sri Lanka, in this paper we attempt to address the question of: What types of university-industry (U-I) collaboration currently exist in Sri Lanka and what value do they create for key stakeholders involved in such partnering arrangements?

We will present some empirical research findings that help us to understanding how universities in Sri Lanka have attempted to initiate collaboration with industrial firms. Universities are constantly looking for new ways to remain relevant actors in the knowledge economy. On the other hand, industrial firms are exploring ways of keeping abreast of technological progress in a highly uncertain competitive environment. Hence both of these actors can help each other via a number of different types of interactions. Here it is worthwhile mentioning the country setting for our research study. Sri Lanka is a developing country with a population of 22 million people and the economy is largely based on agriculture, services, and light industry. The service sector is the largest sector of the Sri Lankan economy, employing 45% of the workforce. Tourism, banking, finance, and retail trade are the major components of the service sector (Bureau of Economic & Business Affairs, 2014).

This paper is structured as follows: we first present some literature insights from previous work undertaken in the study of university-industry collaborations and show where there is potential to add to previous studies in terms of building on existing work; then we briefly the research methods used to capture empirical data. Subsequently, we present the main results and draw out some key implications for different stakeholders, especially in the context of developing countries.

2. Previous work and literature insights

Although universities might seem to fulfill largely similar functions in most industrial economies, the importance of their role differs noticeably across developed and developing economies, as this is influenced by the structure of domestic industry and the size and structure of other publicly funded research performers (Sutthijakra and Intarakumnerd, 2015).

Hence we need a better understanding of why industrial firms in developing countries would benefit from relationships with universities, specifically in a resource constrained environment.

When analyzing university-industry cooperation we need to appreciate that many universities that have little historical experience of initiating such collaborations will need to go through a number of stages during which individuals and organizations become aware of each other, identify a potential partner and engage in preliminary discussions (Plewa et al., 2013). Awareness and contacts have been presented in the literature as likely barriers, given the differences inherent to finding an appropriate partner from either the university or industry side. This barrier is likely to be more acute if firms and universities have little awareness of the opportunities that may be offered by engaging in such collaborations, thus making it more difficult to actually identify suitable contact persons to start the initial dialogue (Galan-Muros and Plewa, 2016). Another barrier to university-industry collaboration often cited in the literature is the lack of funding to support such initiatives. A shortage of such funding, especially via government policy instruments in developing countries, is often identified as an important obstacle to developing university-industry collaborative partnerships (Perkman et al., 2011; Howells et al., 2012). Galan-Muros and Plewa (2016) add that these types of funding barriers can affect not only larger investment strategic partnerships such as research collaborations, but also initiatives like curriculum-design and delivery, lifelong learning, student mobility and professional mobility, which seem especially relevant to the context of developing countries.

Relationships between universities and industrial firms in developing countries have advanced very slowly over recent times, mainly due to divergent viewpoints concerning the merits of such collaborations. For example, in Pakistan, industries demand research in practical fields whereas universities prefer research in their own respective scientific and technological areas (Afzal et al, 2014). But with the passage of time, both industry and universities are realizing the increasing demand for their joint participation in research activities. There are numerous characteristics of universities in developing countries, which themselves impede closer ties to the business and industry sectors. For example in Thailand, many university staffs function on a timeframe that is tied to the semester period of teaching students, whereas private sector businesses expect a much faster turnaround (Brimble and Donor, 2007). In Thailand some university professors enhance their low salaries in the public sector with some consultancy work with the private sector on an informal basis (Schiller and Liefner, 2007). From the Thai Hard Disk Drive (HDD) industry, we learn that the *intermediaries* play an important consulting, brokering, and mediating role to help facilitate university-industry collaboration for this sector in Thailand. According to a survey conducted by Sutthijakra and Intarakumnerd (2015), these intermediaries help alleviate systemic failures by building the recognized network of university and industry, developing human resources and providing resources (i.e. information, training, testing and funding) to university and industry. As a result, interactions and relationships in university-industry partnering are deepened and strengthened.

Since university-industry interactions are a relatively recent occurrence in Sri Lanka, this type of initiative has received limited proper leadership and monitoring from within the university sector. De Silva (2012) infers that it has been historically difficult to stimulate university-industry collaborations in Sri Lanka, partly due to the absence of an overall university policy or support mechanisms to promote academic entrepreneurship. Any such small scale initiatives are principally driven by individual academics. Furthermore, since all the Sri Lankan universities suffered from resource scarcities in recent years, there is no significant difference between universities.

Differences in the organisational culture of universities and business firms has been identified as a barrier to effective collaboration between these two actors, especially so in some developing countries. The literature highlights organisational culture as a barrier as it involves factors such as different motivations, communication modes, time horizons and levels of bureaucracy. Motivations can differ dependent on different institutional norms and resultant goals. While universities typically focus on generating and disseminating new basic knowledge, business commonly seeks directly applicable knowledge to provide short term economic value for firms (Bruneel et al, 2010; Galan-Muros and Plewa, 2016). Although some industrial firms take a long-term approach to their innovation efforts (Perkman et al., 2011), which might result in decreasing the difference in time horizons for university-industry collaborations, in many cases the conception of time regarding project deadlines and results is commonly different between universities and firms (van der Sijde, 2012).

3. Methodology

We have collected empirical data from an exploratory study of university-industry collaborations in Sri Lanka in 2015. In this paper we mainly report on findings related to the following objectives of our study, when exploring evidence of U-I collaborations, especially from the universities perspective:

- To investigate the level of U-I collaboration prevailing in the state universities of Sri Lanka.
- To identify the mode of collaboration with industry.
- To identify factors that motivated the universities to establish collaborations with industry.
- To investigate any major problems related to maintaining existing relationships with industrial firms.
- To investigate factors related to successful relationships with industrial firms.

Eight Sri Lankan state universities were selected for our questionnaire survey. Of these 8 universities, four were established between 1940 to 1960, three between 1970 to 1980 and one university was established in the year 1999. We received 43 completed questionnaire responses to our survey conducted in 2015. The response data was analysed using descriptive statistics. The academics were from a broad range of subject areas including applied sciences, medicine, engineering, and computer science/information technology. We collected data using a survey questionnaire. The majority of the questions on the questionnaire were on Likert-type response scales. However, some for closed-ended questions, we have given the option “other” to add any other relevant responses. To provide more options for academics to respond, we kept some questions open-ended.

One limitation with our study is that at the point of reporting the findings presented in this paper, we have only received limited insights from Sri Lankan industrial firms regarding their perspectives on university-industry collaborations. However, we did speak to a number of different industry sector representatives who attended two workshop forums that we organised on the theme of our project study. These workshops were held in Colombo (Sri Lanka) in June 2015 and December 2015. Hence we have also attempted to incorporate some of the limited key industry perspectives from these two forums within the scope of this paper. However, the main empirical findings reported in the paper remain the insights received from the questionnaire surveys that were distributed to the Sri Lankan universities.

4. Main empirical findings

With respect to the level of U-I collaboration prevailing in the state universities of Sri Lanka, some of our survey findings show that 35% of the respondents confirmed that their university has an industrial liaison office (or technology transfer unit), while 65% stated their university does not have such an office. 97% of the respondents stated that their university does have some form of collaboration with an industrial firm while only 3% stated having no such collaborations. Furthermore, 96% stated that they have observed their university’s collaboration with industry has increased in the last 5 years while only 3% stated their university’s collaboration with industry remained the same in the last 5 years.

With respect to the mode of collaboration with industry, as highlighted in **Table 1** below, the majority of U-I collaborations followed by Sri Lankan universities appear to be through ‘student placements in industry’ and ‘consultancy to industry by academic staff’.

Table 1. Modes of collaboration with industry

Mode of collaboration pursued by universities in Sri Lanka	% of responses (choose as many boxes as is applicable)
1. Student placements in industry	96.4
2. Consultancy to industry by Academic staff	92.6
3. Research contracted to university staff	76.9
4. Training of industry staff at university	76.9
5. Joint research project/ or joint publication	73.1
6. Industry staff on visiting placement in university	65.4
7. Joint Conference or Seminar event	63
8. Licensing technologies (e.g. patents) to industrial firm	57.7

We explored the factors that motivated the universities to establish collaborations with industry. **Table 2** illustrates what was the most important factor that motivated universities to seek out collaborative opportunities with industry partners. Here the most important factor highlighted is ‘personal contact’. This seems to be mainly via former university students approaching individual university academics or departments to initiate some form of interaction. This could also be initiated at a personal level where university and industry staffs have met at past conferences or seminars.

Table 2. Factors that motivated the universities to establish collaborations with industry

Most important factor that motivates university to collaborate with an industrial firm	% of responses (choose only one option)
1. Personal contact	86.7
2. Through your university/institution's initiatives	13.3
3. Through a Government scheme/programme that intends to enhance university and industry linkages	0
4. Chamber of Commerce	0
Total	100

We questioned whether universities participate in Government funded schemes for working with industry. **Table 3** shows results relating to participation of universities in any Government funded schemes/projects for working with industry, as national public funded schemes are seen as an important policy instrument to help trigger U-I collaborations in some developing countries. We identified the following from secondary information sources as the **three main government led mechanisms** promoting U-I collaborations in the chronological order of implementation:

1. The Sri Lankan government formally started to support university-industry interactions from 2005, when the *University Grants Commission – Sri Lanka* (UGC) introduced the circular promoting university-industry collaborations. Under this initiative, the UGC grants one year leave for senior university academics to work in any industrial establishment (University Grants Commission – Sri Lanka).
2. In 2014, the government of Sri Lanka introduced a mechanism of triple tax deduction from the industry if they collaborate with universities in doing research (Budget speech 2014).
3. The latest initiative introduced in 2015 provides some funding that could include an element of U-I interaction within the following areas: (1) research and innovation in universities – pure sciences; (2) research that directly impact on communities; (3) post-doctoral research for academic staff just completed their PhDs; (4) local and international training for university academics; and (5) soft loans for academics to commercialize products developed through R&D (University Grants Commission – Sri Lanka).

Table 3. Participation of universities in any Government funded schemes/projects for working with industry

Has your university participated in any Government funded schemes/projects for working with industry?	% of responses
Yes	37.0
No	63.0
Total	100

For those universities that have some experience of collaborating with industry, **Table 4** highlights the main challenges (or problems) faced in maintaining relationships with industrial firms. Highest number of respondents identified 'organizational bureaucracy' as the main barrier to maintain existing relationships with industrial firms. The second most frequently cited reason was 'high teaching workload'.

Table 4. Problems related to maintaining existing relationships with industrial firms

Main problems in maintaining U-I linkages (from university respondents)
1. Organizational bureaucracy
2. High teaching workload
3. Different interests among the academic and industry
4. Academics do not see the importance of university-industry relationship
5. Lack of support for industrial research from government
6. Lack of understanding on time taken to do a collaborative research project
7. Industry not interested in research or publications
8. Firms lack appreciation of university research
9. Academics lack knowledge of industry requirements

Note: This is an open ended question.

Finally, as illustrated in **Table 5** below, we questioned the most important factors related to successful relationships with industrial firms. Highest number of respondents identified ‘mutual benefits’, followed by ‘ease of access to firms’ and ‘maintaining of common set of goals’ as the most important factors for enabling successful collaborations with industry.

Table 5. Factors related to successful relationships with industrial firms

1. Mutual benefits
2. Ease of access to firms
3. Maintenance of common set of goals
4. Frequent discussions/feedback
5. Mutual trust
6. Government support on private-public partnerships
7. Positive attitude of key industry managers

Note: This is an open ended question.

We held *two workshops in Sri Lanka* (June 2015 and December 2015, both in Colombo) focusing on the theme of university-industry interactions in developing countries. The first workshop was for industry practitioners and the second attracted some industry professionals along with representation from universities and some national agencies/scientific research organizations. Both workshop participants highlighted a number of existing challenges that might inhibit university-industry collaborations in Sri Lanka. They also provided some suggestions of how to address and overcome some of these challenges. Within the scope of this paper, we briefly highlight a few key issues arising from the workshops.

Industrial firms from the private sector, as well as trade associations need to be made aware of the diversity of linkages that can be formed directly and indirectly with universities. Hence there appears to be a lack of understanding about what each of the partners can bring to such collaborations. This is partly linked to the fact that outputs of firms are perceived to be more practical based and outputs from universities are less practical and possibly more theoretical based. Hence there needs to be some mechanism to advance the understanding of what the universities and firms can offer to each other. One suggestion made is to create a national institute that acts as an industry-universities coordination type body, which can highlight the benefits of university-industry partnerships to both universities and firms and it can set-up some forums that bring together these key actors at conference/ seminar type events to gain an improved understanding of the requirements of potential collaborators. Here it was also mentioned that the government can play an important role by helping to set-up such a national coordination body. From the industry side this was also seen as an enabler of building trust and confidence in each other’s ability to collaborate and deliver results beneficial for both partners. Some industry professionals indicated that the current level of collaboration with universities varies with the firm size. For example, some large firms have stronger motivations to consider strategic level collaborations with universities, whereas it is more challenging for SMEs to mobilise resources and initiate such collaborations with universities.

Another key issue raised in the workshops was that university students could also act as facilitators of collaboration and other forms of knowledge transfer between universities and the private sector. For example, it was mentioned that some universities now offer some of their students’ openings to implement some of their research projects with industry partners, so this could be extended in the future. Where practicable, some university departments may consider working closely with industry for support with curriculum development whereby students are graduating with the skills that will help them to secure company based jobs after completing their studies (for undergraduates and postgraduates) as industrial firms would be able to benefit from recruiting students with both academic and practical related skills.

5. Key implications

As shown earlier in the paper, since university-industry interactions in Sri Lanka is a relatively recent phenomenon it has received limited proper leadership and direction or monitoring from within the university sector. Hence, in line with an earlier suggestion by Esham’s (2008), we believe it may be appropriate to consider the setting-up of a higher level body to provide direction to industry interaction cells setup at universities. This higher body should comprise representatives from both the universities and the industry in advisory capacities and ought to recruit personnel with solid leadership qualities and experience in industry and university affairs to provide the much needed guidance to the cells at universities. As far as industry is concerned, given the scale and diversity of local industries it is highly unlikely for each firm to come up with a liaison office of its own to interact with universities. Hence, Esham (2008)

recommended that the more feasible approach could be to setup liaison offices with the involvement of the industry association like the chambers of commerce and industry.

Many universities in developed countries and some in developing countries have created Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) to deal with issues related to patenting, licensing and new venture creation based on university owned intellectual property. Hence when initiating university-industry collaborations in developing countries, the key actors or government agencies involved with this type of initiative should perhaps examine any evaluation reports from countries that have TTOs to learn about the governance structure of the TTOs within a university setting, how well they have helped to spin-out companies and technology licenses from universities. These types of policy instrument evaluations may also highlight some key firm motivations to collaborate with universities. For example, is the remit classified as research, education, technology transfer, dissemination, networking or any other objective? These objectives might be viewed as investments in specific collaborative activities with a university and the projected values could be compared with the firm's financial commitment and other forms of *in-kind support*, to evaluate how the firm perceived such types of collaboration. These issues are connected to the point that both parties (i.e. the firm and the university) must be conscious of the potential pitfalls of university-industry collaboration before entering into such agreements. A previous U.K. based survey identified 'divergence of objectives' between the university and industry participants as the most frequently cited problem area in university-industry collaborations (Howells et al, 1997). The divergence could be caused by changes in priorities on the industrial firm side, sometimes driven by changes in management structure or ownership, or on the academic side, driven by cultural issues that may steer the research in a different path. To help mitigate this problem, the sponsor companies should try to manage the connection better and cautiously over time.

With respect to the main modes of collaboration with industry currently being undertaken by universities, the university respondents rated 'student placement in industry' and 'consultancy to industry by Academic staff' as the most significant modes of collaboration in our survey of Sri Lankan universities. This issue was also confirmed by industry professionals at both of our workshop forums, where student placements and industry input into curriculum development may be beneficial for both students and industry. One key implication for Sri Lanka and many other developing countries, is that universities could design more undergraduate programs (e.g. in fields of physical sciences, agricultural sciences, engineering and IT) with a one-year industry placement, where a student takes a break from academic study for one year to work in industry and then comes back to university to complete the final year of a bachelors/ masters program. Here the academic professors delivering the sandwich degree programs should visit students during the industry placement year, as it connects them with some latest developments in industry, as well as helping them to understand the context of the work in which the students are engaged. This should also help students in giving them a better idea about their career paths before they leave university as it ought to encourage them to think about the type of industrial setting they might wish to work in as well as encouraging some students with an entrepreneurial flair to think about starting their own business in the future. Another advantage for the student returning from an industrial placement year is that he or she can work on more practical based problems at university, which might have arisen from their placement organization. This should lead to a useful fusion of work and academic perspective for the students. However, one important caveat to remember here is that the primary purpose of a university course is to educate students and not simply prepare them for the world of work. Here industrial firms also have some responsibility to continue to educate graduates at work to 'counter the argument that graduates should be expected to possess all the technical and soft skills under their belt on day one of joining a company after graduating from university'. Hence what students learn from their various contacts with industry is not simply aimed at employability, but is put to good use during the rest of their course of study and any future plans for study perhaps at postgraduate level or during future short executive education type training courses.

As mentioned in some of the literature, good personal contacts also positively impact on university-industry collaboration initiatives, especially because general institutional trust does not exist among the science base and industry in many developing countries yet Schiller and Lee (2015). University-industry collaboration involving R&D projects and some research commercialization activities have profited from good personal relationships; most likely due to their greater complexity and high levels of risk (Plewa and Quester, 2006). Indeed, our survey results from Sri Lanka show that personal contact is the most important factor in facilitating university-industry relationships, confirming that regardless of the institution setting, funding and other factors, developing such relationships is often a person to person mechanism based on building trust, commitment and shared goals (Galan-Muros and Plewa, 2016). This also links to the fact that the focus of university-industry collaborations in some developing countries, should be on projects that can be managed, and whose results can be implemented by the collaborating partners given their limited capabilities. If the remit of such projects might be too complex or uncertain, then the risk of failure and 'loss of trust' is very high while the potential of valuable outcomes remains rather low.

Some university-industry collaborations can be regarded as a strategic partnership for the industrial firms as it offers a number of benefits. One key benefit is that the research collaboration might lead to work on developing technologies and product prototypes that might not presently exist, enabling the industry partner to target potential new markets. Similarly, university academics and research staff can profit from longer-term collaborations by getting a better

understanding of business setting complexities that the industry partner firm is immersed in. Some industrial firms considering investment in more long-term university-industry collaborations are likely to want to know in what ways they could measure the success of entering into this type of partnership. Perkman et al. (2011) state that a suitable measure for the emergence of valuable new ideas from such university-industry collaborations is the number of new early-stage projects that have come about as a result of the alliance. Hence this is one impact of the collaboration. Another impact of collaboration consists of benefits such as recruiting trained graduate and post-graduate students, building wider networks within the academic and industrial communities and take-up of new techniques, methods or approaches within the firm.

6. Conclusion

Dissemination of our research findings is important not only for universities and industry in Sri Lanka, but university academics/ administrators, company managers and policy analysts in other developing countries who may be dealing with similar initiatives to promote university-industry collaboration in their countries. We also suggest that resource constraints in developing countries do not entirely inhibit university-industry connections. In fact, some university academics do actively attempt to overcome various resource barriers. Hence this demonstrates that there are potential opportunities open to those academics, with the right level of institutional support and backing, to initiate such linkages.

In Sri Lanka and some other developing countries, universities are not yet fully accustomed to the idea of starting up new companies through spin-offs. They are however, part of the larger community, and they perhaps need to recognize that they have a third mission, which embraces the need to contribute to regional economic development. This of course requires the government to earmark funding and other support to public universities in order for the universities to realize the third mission. Typically there is a lack of infrastructure, skills and resources required to support academic entrepreneurship and academic-industry collaborations.

Our empirical findings have shown some important motivations as to why universities would consider collaborating with industry. But at the same time there appear to be a number of challenges that need to be addressed if universities are to interact with industry more commonly in Sri Lanka. These, as notes above, appear to be around relevance, where alignment between industry and universities appears to be weak, especially for many SME firms. Hence, one major issue remains simple ignorance by firms of what universities do and what they could provide in terms of knowledge and support for industry. Similarly, some universities seem to be unaware of the range of different mechanisms available to explore collaborations and interaction with industrial firms. As mentioned in our findings, more awareness raising about the potential benefits of university-industry collaboration and its value to different stakeholder groups is required, and this must often start at a national level through some policy instruments that support these types of initiatives.

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